

TABLE II

Water taken.	Conc. of water in reaction mixture.	Water found.	% Error.
0.2267 g.	0.45 %	0.2259 g.	-0.35
0.1427	0.23	0.1416	-0.77
0.0918	0.46	0.0910	-0.87
0.0825	0.41	0.0827	+0.25
0.0480	0.16	0.0485	+1.04
0.0468	0.09	0.0470	+0.43

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INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR
THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA-32.

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF HYDROXYLAMINE

BY S. S. MUHAMMAD AND T. NAVANEETH RAO

The present work was undertaken in order to check independently the value of the dissociation constant of hydroxylamine, obtained conductometrically in this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 101). Experiments showed that in the case of hydroxylamine, the method of Stenström and Goldsmith (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1683) was the most suitable.

Hydroxylamine is known to be highly diastinctive in the aqueous solution (Hartley and Dobbie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 318) as in the gas phase (Smith and Leighton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 172); it exhibits continuous absorption in the region 2015 to 2350 Å or further, depending on the length of the optical path and the concentration or pressure of hydroxylamine. This shows that unlike aniline (Flexser *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1935, 57, 2103) and pyridine (Andon *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 910) here concentrated solutions and longer optical paths have to be used.

The apparatus consisted of a Unicam quartz spectrophotometer (model Sp. 500), a hydrogen lamp combined with a stabilised power pack and quartz cells of 4 cm optical path. A series of phosphate buffers (p_H 2 to 11) made from $M/10-H_3PO_4$ and $M/10-KOH$ were prepared and their p_H was determined on a Beckman model-G p_H -meter, previously standardised against standard buffers.

Pure hydroxylamine was prepared by the method of Hurd and Brownstein (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 67). It was dissolved in water to form a strong solution, the strength of which was determined by the bromate method. It was then diluted to $\sim M/2$; 1 c.c. of this was diluted to 25 c.c. by adding the required buffer. Tests showed that this solution had the same p_H as the original buffer. The blank contained the appropriate buffer to which 1 c.c. of distilled water was added. The absorption measurements were

taken in the range 2100 to 2400 Å at the room temperature of 30° which varied within $\pm 0.5^\circ$ during the experiments. The data so obtained may be used to construct spectrophotometric titration curves at desired wave-lengths. A graph of absorbance against pH at 2120 Å is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG 1

To find the mid-point of the break in the curve, a graphical analysis as suggested by Slabaugh and Cates (*Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 151), was carried out by bisecting the distance between the linear portions of the curve prior to and following the inflexion. This gave a pK value of 6.28 at 2120 Å. Similar treatments of the data at 2140, 2160 and 2180 Å yield the values 6.27, 6.25 and 6.25 respectively. The mean 6.263 is the apparent pK value. The apparent dissociation constant is related with the thermodynamic dissociation constant by the relation :

$$pK_A = pK + \log_{10} \gamma BH^+$$

where pK_A refers to thermodynamic equilibrium :

and γBH^+ is the activity coefficient of the base cation $(NH_2OH)^+$. The latter can be calculated from the approximate Debye-Hückel equation :

$$\log_{10} \gamma BH^+ = \frac{-0.5 z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$$

where z denotes valency of the base cation, equal to 1 for hydroxylamine, and μ = ionic strength of the medium. At pH 6.25 the phosphoric acid - KOH mixture corresponds to an ionic strength $\sqrt{\mu} = 0.264$ and $\log_{10} \gamma BH^+ = -0.105$, which makes $pK_A = 6.158$. But the basic dissociation constant pK_B for the equilibrium :

can be obtained from the relation

$$pK_B = pK_w - pK_A.$$

According to Harned and Owen ("Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", p. 485, Reinhold Pub. 2nd edition) pK_w at 30° is 13.833. Therefore pK_a at $30^\circ = 7.675$ and $K_a = 2.113 \times 10^{-8}$. This compares closely with the value 2.202×10^{-8} for the dissociation constant derived from conductometric determination of the hydrolysis of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, reported previously (*loc. cit.*).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
OSMANIA UNIVERSITY,
HYDER ABAD-DECCAN.

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REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE BY FERROCYANIDE

By K. CHATTERJEE AND B. P. GYANI

Much interesting information is available regarding the oxidising properties of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. Its reduction by iodide ions was studied potentiometrically in detail by Gyani and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 561; 1955, 32, 313). The reduction of the dichromate ion by the ferrocyanide ion was first studied potentiometrically by Someya (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 158), who found that the redox reaction

could be followed potentiometrically at 40° - 65° in 5 to 10 c.c. HCl per 60 c.c. of the total volume.

Someya's work refers to strictly specified conditions. The present work was taken up to carry out a fuller investigation of this reaction in different concentrations of two different acids at ordinary temperatures. The use of potassium ferrocyanide for standardisation of potassium permanganate solution is well known. It is of interest to know whether the ferrocyanide itself could be standardised with a readily available substance like $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

A. R. grade $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was taken and prepared for use as usual. Finely powdered crystals of A. R. $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ were dried to a constant weight over a saturated solution of NaBr (Vogel, "Quantitative Analysis", London, 1951, p. 271). Titrations were carried out in a three-necked Woulff's bottle in which 100 c.c. of 0.005 M solutions of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in different concentrations of sulphuric acid (12N, 8N, 6N, 4N, 2N, N, N/2, N/4, and N/10) and HCl (2N, N, N/2, and N/4) were taken. The titrations were carried out in the usual manner, using a bright platinum foil electrode at $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ for H_2SO_4 mixtures and at $34^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ for HCl mixtures.

The inflexions are quite steep in each case. When sulphuric acid concentrations lie between 6N and 1N or when HCl concentrations lie between N/2 and N/4, the inflexions correspond to 6 moles $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ per mole dichromate and the following mechanism is indicated:

Steady potentials are obtained in 15 to 20 minutes of each addition of the titrant and this period is somewhat longer when the acid concentrations are lower. It appears therefore